

Map of extreme sunsets of Europe

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The touristic activities related with the observation of sunsets are gaining interest in Europe. For this reason, we calculate the map of points and calendar to observe the last sunset in Europe along the year (excluding remote locations such as Iceland or Açores and Faroe Islands). Due to the changing orientation of the Earth with respect to the sun, the result is a list of places that starts in Portugal in winter and then moves north to locations in Ireland and Norway. We calculate also national relevant points for Spain, France and the United Kingdom.

Keywords: sunset; terminator; Europe; coastal tourism; Atlantic area

- We calculate the locations for observing the last sunset in Europe on any day of the year.
- We also calculate relevant locations for observing the last sunset, nationally, in some European countries.
- This opens the door to launching timed proposals that target this attractive of these locations.

1. Introduction

In 2016 a study identified the places along the coast of Europe from which the last sunset of mainland Europe can be observed (Mira-Pérez, 2018). The association of such a label to a specific place increases its attractiveness from a touristic point of view. Spain has explored the charm of sunsets all along its geography (Fascinating Spain, n.d.) and provides a good example of the practical application of this kind of research. It is the second most visited country in the world (after France) in 2023, with a very important growth in 2024 (more than 90 million international visitors), with tourism accounting for 12.3% of the country's gross domestic product (Associated Press, 2025); therefore, any innovation in this subject is welcome.

In the autonomous region of Galicia (the westernmost region of mainland Spain), where one of these spots to observe the last sunset is located, this result prompted several actions in the touristic sector, both at the local and institutional levels (Xunta de Galicia, n.d.). It has also been the origin of an agreement with Japan, on the basis of the synchronization of sunrise and sunset, on specific significant days, at two scenarios recognized as World Heritage by UNESCO: the sunrise at the endpoint of the Japanese Kumano Kodo (the spiritual pilgrimage route of Japan), in Nachikatsuura (Wakayama Prefecture) and the European Way of Saint James (Camino de Santiago, one of the most important pilgrimage routes in the Catholic world) at Fisterra (Galicia) (La Voz de Galicia, 2023).

Also, it has inspired a new research initiative involving Portugal, Spain, France and Ireland (Atlantic Sunset Project, n.d.; Lois González et al, 2024), which was selected to celebrate, on this basis, the Interreg Cooperation Day in the Atlantic Area of the European Union (Interreg Cooperation Day – Atlantic Area, 2025). In this new framework, it is necessary to calculate a new map of relevant points of sunsets in Western Europe.

2. Methods

The 23.5° axial tilt of the Earth dictates the angle of the terminator, the boundary between daylight and darkness. Only at the equinoxes does this line precisely coincide with meridians (lines of longitude). During the summer months, the terminator stretches from northeast to southwest, and in winter, it spans from southeast to northwest. As a result, the geographic location experiencing the latest sunset within a given region varies significantly with the seasons.

This work aims to pinpoint locations in European countries along the Atlantic coast where the latest sunset occurs right on the sea line to identify locations with the latest sunset at national level and globally in Europe. Table 1 and figure 1 list the places of interest in Portugal, Spain, Ireland, France, United Kingdom and Norway. In our analysis, we did not consider Açores (Portugal), Iceland, and Faroe Islands (Denmark) due to their remote position from the European continent.

In each country we selected a NW extreme point to be associated with the latest sunset in summer, and a SW extreme point to be associated with the latest sunset in winter. In Ireland, Portugal, and United Kingdom we also selected a W extreme point, which happens to be the latest sunset around the equinoxes.

On this basis, we wrote a script in Octave to:

1. Compute the solar declination on every day of the year 2025, assisted by xplanet (<http://xplanet.sourceforge.net>), which was also used to generate the orthographic projections and labels shown in the illustrations.
2. Compute the equation of time, i.e., the discrepancy between apparent solar time and mean solar time (Koblick, 2025).

3. Compute sunset times for every location and every calendar date in 2025 considering the formula for sun height as a function of solar declination and geographical position (Pierrehumbert, 2010). The sunset was defined by the crossing of the solar upper limb and simulated by a solar altitude $z=z_0-A\sqrt{H}$, where $z_0=-0.85^\circ$, H is observer's height and $A=-0.0293^\circ \text{ m}^{-1/2}$ (Bowditch2002).

3. Results

The script referred above resulted in a matrix A with $m=365$ rows (one per day) and $n=15$ columns (one per location). Each element A_{ji} shows the sunset time for location i and for calendar date j . To illustrate the varying conditions throughout one year Figure 2 displays the evolution of sunset lines in Aghernagallagh (Ireland). Solar declination, a proxy for calendar date, is represented by a gradient color from blue (winter) to red (summer).

The matrix served to identify extreme sunsets according to calendar date globally and by country or area of interest. Table 2 lists the global results. The extreme sunset moves from SW Portugal to W Portugal on February 21st. Then, by March 14th, the extreme sunset moves to W Ireland, and soon (March 29) to NW Ireland. One month later, the extreme sunset occurs in NW UK, in the Outer Hebrides. Finally, on May 4th, Northern Norway takes preference. From early August to mid-October the reverse sequence occurs. Figure 3 visualizes this sequence helped with sunset lines at specific δ_s values that yield extreme sunsets in every location listed in Table 2. Note that above the Polar Circle there is actually no sunset (midnight sun) during the summer months.

3.1. Analysis by country

Table 3 lists the extreme sunset points in Portugal, Spain, France, Ireland, Great Britain (island) and Norway, with Figure 4 showing the corresponding sunset lines.

In Portugal we selected a SW location (Sao Vicente), a W location (Cabo da Roca) and a NW location (Farol de Monterol). The extreme sunset shifts smoothly from one location to the other.

In Spain we selected the NW location of Cabo Touriñán (the Westernmost point in mainland Spain), which happens to be the extreme sunset in Continental Europe from March 24 to April 23 and from August 18 to September 19 (see Mira-Pérez, 2018)) and the SW location of Ayamonte in the mouth of the river Guadiana that separates Spain and Portugal. Cabo Touriñán happens to be the extreme sunset in mainland Spain when $\delta_s > -11$ (mid-February to mid-October). When $\delta_s = -11$, the terminator line goes from Cabo Touriñán through the Atlantic Ocean to Ayamonte without touching mainland Spain.

In France a similar scenario occurs between the Westernmost location (Point de Corsen) and Point Saint-Anne a SW point located in the Franco-spanish border. When $\delta_s > -16.7$ (early February to early November) the extreme sunset occurs in Point de Corsen and at $\delta_s = -16.7$ the extreme sunset shifts to Point Saint-Anne, see Figure 4.

The extreme sunsets in Ireland are associated with three locations: Dursey Point (SW), Dunmore Head (Westernmost) and Aghernagallagh (NW). Dunmore Head is the extreme sunset from mid-February mid-March and mid-September to mid-October. Dursey Point takes prevalence when $\delta_s < -11$ and Aghernagallagh when $\delta_s > 3$.

We found interesting to analyze the case of the island of Great Britain separately (i.e., excluding Northern Ireland, the Hebrides and the Northern Isles). We then considered Land's End (SW tip in Cornwall), Corrachadh Mòr (the Westernmost tip of the island) and Cape Wrath as a NW location. We found that Land's End is the extreme sunset in the

island from late September to mid-March when $\delta_s < -2$. Then Corrachadh Mòr takes precedence from mid-March to mid-April and late August to late September. Finally, Cape Wrath is the extreme sunset in the island when $\delta_s > 9$, from mid-April to late August. We also considered three locations in Norway, Farsund (a SW location), Vardetangen (Western most tip in Norway) and Nordkapp. Table 3 and figure 4 lists the results from this analysis. However, this should be taken as merely descriptive because: (i) the coast of Norway is complicated due to the abundance of fjords and elevated viewpoints; (ii) the Western coast of Norway aligns with the terminator line from 61 latitude to 70 latitude when $\delta_s = 14.5$; (iii) unlike what happens in France, Spain or Portugal, a plurality of locations around the Southern coast of Norway show the extreme sunset time around the winter solstice.

4. Conclusion

In the search for the place to observe the last sunset in Europe (that changes over the course of the year due to the changing orientation of the Earth's rotation axis), we have written a script in Octave to compute the solar declination on every day of the year 2025 in Western shores of the continent and the British Isles. We have computed sunset times for every location and every calendar date in 2025 considering the equation of time, geographical coordinates, and the formula for sun height as a function of solar declination and time.

With this, we have calculated the map of points and calendar to observe the last sunsets in Europe along the year (excluding the remote cases of Iceland, Açores and Faroe Islands). The result is a list of places that starts in Portugal in winter and then moves north to locations in Ireland, the Outer Hebrides and Norway. We calculate also national relevant points for Spain, France and the Great Britain (island). This opens the possibility

of launching timed proposals that target specific characteristics of the locations with latest sunset either at a country level or at Europe level.

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Declarations

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare

Data available on request to the authors.

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Tables and figures

	Location		Latitude	Longitude
1	Dunmore Head	IE	52.109°	−10.482°
2	Dursey Point	IE	51.579°	−10.235°
3	Aghernagallagh	IE	54.269°	−10.082°
4	Cabo da Roca	PT	38.783°	−9.500°
5	Cabo Touriñán	ES	43.050°	−9.300°
6	Cabo São Vicente	PT	37.017°	−8.994°
7	Farol de Montedor	PT	41.751°	−8.873°
8	Ayamonte	ES	37.174°	−7.355°
9	Aird Uig	UK	58.244°	−7.024°
10	Corrachadh Mòr	UK	56.700°	−6.217°
11	Land's End	UK	50.064°	−5.715°
12	Cape Wrath	UK	58.626°	−5.005°
13	Pointe de Corsen	FR	48.433°	−4.897°
14	Pointe Sainte-Anne	FR	43.385°	−1.753°
15	Vardetangen	NO	60.810°	4.945°
16	Farsund	NO	58.088°	6.593°
17	Nordkapp	NO	71.206°	25.784°

Table 1. List of places of interest in connection with sunsets ordered by increasing longitude. The second column shows the alpha-2 iso 3166-1 country code. Latitude and longitude are given in decimal format up to 1/1000 of degree or 3.6 seconds of arc. Figure 1 shows a cartography.

	Location	Start δ_s	Start date	Time
6	Cabo São Vicente		01-Jan	
4	Cabo da Roca	-10.8°	21-Feb	17:53
1	Dunmore Head	-2.9°	14-Mar	18:23
3	Aghernagallagh	3.1°	29-Mar	18:58
9	Aird Uig	11.6°	21-Apr	19:54
17	Nordkapp	15.7°	04-May	20:24
9	Aird Uig	16.1°	09-Aug	20:21
3	Aghernagallagh	12.0°	22-Aug	19:52
1	Dunmore Head	3.3°	15-Sep	19:09
4	Cabo da Roca	-2.5°	30-Sep	18:44
6	Cabo São Vicente	-10.4°	21-Oct	18:24

Table 2. List of extreme sunsets in Europe. See table 1 for the geographical coordinates of the locations. Start δ_s lists the value of the solar declination when the referred place takes precedence over the previous listed place. Start date lists the calendar date at that moment. The last column shows the sunset time (UTC) for that date. Figure 3 shows a cartography.

	Location	Start δ_s	Start date	Time
PORTUGAL				
6	Cabo São Vicente		01-Jan	
4	Cabo da Roca	-10.8°	21-Feb	17:53
7	Farol de Montedor	2.7°	28-Mar	18:46
4	Cabo da Roca	3.0°	16-Sep	18:57
6	Cabo São Vicente	-10.4°	21-Oct	18:24
SPAIN				
8	Ayamonte		01-Jan	
5	Cabo Touriñán	-11.6°	19-Feb	17:44
8	Ayamonte	-11.1°	23-Oct	18:15
FRANCE				
14	Pointe Sainte-Anne		01-Jan	
13	Pointe de Corsen	-16.8°	03-Feb	16:52
14	Pointe Sainte-Anne	-16.6°	09-Nov	17:23
IRLEAND				
2	Dursey Point		01-Jan	
1	Dunmore Head	-10.8°	21-Feb	17:37
3	Aghernagallagh	3.1°	29-Mar	18:58
1	Dunmore Head	3.3°	15-Sep	19:09
2	Dursey Point	-10.4°	21-Oct	18:09
GREAT BRITAIN (ISLAND)				
11	Land's End		01-Jan	
10	Corrachadh Mòr	-2.5°	15-Mar	18:07
12	Cape Wrath	8.7°	13-Apr	19:25
10	Corrachadh Mòr	9.3°	30-Aug	19:28
11	Land's End	-2.1°	29-Sep	18:28
NORWAY				
16	Farsund		01-Jan	
15	Vardetangen	-9.4°	25-Feb	16:25
17	Nordkapp	13.2°	26-Apr	19:30
15	Vardetangen	13.4°	18-Aug	19:25
16	Farsund	-9.3°	18-Oct	16:54

Table 3. List of extreme sunsets in Europe by country or area of interest. See table 1 for the geographical coordinates of the locations. Start δ_s lists the value of the solar declination when the referred place takes precedence over the previous listed place. Start date lists the calendar date at that moment. The last column shows the sunset time (UTC) for that date. Figure 4 shows a cartography.

Figure 1. Map of Europe indicating the places of interest (black dots) in the Western shores of the continent and the British Isles. See in Table 1 for the numerical codes.

Figure 2. The yearly evolution of sunset lines at Aghernagallagh (Ireland). The color map shows the solar declination and goes from blue (winter solstice, $\delta_s = -23.5$) to red (summer solstice, $\delta_s = 23.5$) with white representing the Equinoxes ($\delta_s = 0$). The lines visualize the field locations that share sunset with Aghernagallagh twice a year, and the regions where the sunset always happens before or after the Irish location.

Figure 3. The evolution of extreme sunset points in Europe. The colored lines show the terminator at specific δ_s (-23 , -5 , 2 , 10 , 15 and 17 ; color map shown in Figure 2), following the results in Table 2. For every displayed line the extreme sunset occurs at a different location.

Figure 4. The evolution of extreme sunset points per country or area of interest. From top to bottom and left to right: Ireland, Great Britain (island), Norway; Portugal, Spain and France. The colored lines show the terminator at specific δ_s (color map shown in Figure 2) following the results in Table 3. For every displayed line the extreme sunset in the panel occurs at a different location.